

The Influence of Financial News Sentiment on Investor Behaviour and Market Dynamics: A Machine Learning Approach to Sentiment Classification

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Abstract

Financial news sentiment influences investor decisions, but most research focuses on market-level outcomes rather than how individual investors with different personalities interpret the same news. We combined a Random Forest sentiment classifier (80.2% accuracy on FinancialPhraseBank) with a multi-agent simulation using FinBERT on 2,263 expert-labeled headlines, producing 226,300 decisions across 100 agents with randomized perception, portfolio memory, and herding dynamics. The clearest result was about neutral headlines: agents agreed on only 89.4% of neutral headlines compared to 98–99% for positive and negative, which mirrors the classifier’s 26% neutral error rate. Herding cascades appeared in 32.8% (buy) and 16.0% (sell) of headlines, but ablation tests showed cascades barely changed when the herding mechanism was turned off, meaning agents were independently reaching the same conclusion rather than copying each other. A small shift toward caution appeared but was too small to be meaningful. Overall, neutral sentiment appears to be where both classification and investor agreement break down.

1 Introduction

The Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) says markets are fully rational and that prices reflect all available information (Lo, 2018). However, research shows that investors often react emotionally to how information is presented, not just to the facts (Lucey & Dowling, 2005). Tetlock (2007) showed that media pessimism predicts downward pressure on stock prices using a large dataset of Wall Street Journal columns, and Baker & Wurgler (2006) demonstrated that investor sentiment predicts future stock returns: when investors are overly optimistic, speculative stocks tend to perform poorly afterward. But most of this research looks at the market as a whole. Less work has been done on how individual differences between investors shape their responses to the same headlines. Two people can read the same earnings report and walk away with opposite conclusions about what to do.

Part of why this happens is cognitive biases. Financial news sentiment, meaning the emotional tone in financial texts (Schumaker et al., 2012), can trigger biases like confirmation bias, recency bias, and overconfidence (Tetlock, 2007; Bihari et al., 2025; Kahneman, 2011). Fear and greed can amplify these effects (Shefrin, 2000), and when investors start copying each other instead of thinking independently, the result is herding, which can lead to bubbles and crashes (Devenow & Welch, 1996).

Recent advances in financial sentiment analysis use AI models like FinBERT, which outperform traditional models like Random Forests (Araci, 2019). In this study, we combine a machine learning sentiment classifier with a multi-agent simulation to explore how investor personality affects the interpretation of financial news. We used the FinancialPhraseBank dataset (Malo et al., 2014), where 5 to 8 annotators with backgrounds in finance and business independently classified each headline, and used these labels as the basis for our simulation.

2 Theoretical Framework

2.1 Mathematical Model of Sentiment-Influenced Decision Making

Baker & Wurgler (2006) showed that investor sentiment can be measured and that it pushes decisions away from what purely rational models would predict. We describe the relationship between news sentiment and investing behavior with a simple model. Let α represent an investor’s starting allocation, and β their allocation after reading news:

$$\beta = \alpha + \delta(s, b, t) \quad (1)$$

where $s \in \{-1, 0, 1\}$ is the headline sentiment (negative, neutral, positive), b captures how easily the investor is influenced, and t is exposure time. The δ term shows how much a person adjusts their choices based on the tone, their sensitivity to it, and how long they thought about it. In our simulation, b maps to a combination of each agent’s optimism bias, reaction style, and herd susceptibility, while s is sampled randomly from FinBERT’s output rather than taken as a fixed score.

This model is simple on purpose. It does not capture interactions between the parameters, nonlinear effects, or the many other factors that go into real investment decisions. We use it to organize our observations, not as a predictive tool.

2.2 Hypothesis Development

According to Prospect Theory (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979), people dislike losses more than they value equivalent gains. The standard estimate is that losses are felt about twice as strongly as gains of the same size. This means positive news should push investors toward riskier behavior (they do not want to miss out), while negative news should make them pull back (they want to avoid further losses).

Based on this, we came up with three hypotheses. H1: Positive sentiment will lead to more buying among simulated agents. H2: Negative sentiment will lead to more selling, and over time the simulation’s loss-weighted memory mechanism will push agents toward caution. H3: Neutral sentiment will produce the most disagreement among agents, since without a clear signal, personality differences should matter more.

3 Materials and Methods

3.1 Dataset Selection

We used the Financial PhraseBank dataset (Malo et al., 2014) because it is labeled by people with backgrounds in finance, it captures the tone of financial writing, and it includes a mix of positive, negative, and neutral statements. Rather than collecting new behavioral data, we relied on these labels, where 5 to 8 annotators independently classified each headline. For the simulation, we used the Sentences_AllAgree subset (2,263 headlines: 1,390 neutral, 570 positive, 303 negative) where all annotators agreed on the label. For the Random Forest, we used the full dataset (4,846 headlines) to have more training data.

3.2 Machine Learning Methodology

We tested two models: the Random Forest (Breiman, 2001) and the Shallow Neural Network. The Random Forest works by building many decision trees and combining their answers to make a final prediction. It gives good accuracy and is easy to interpret. The Shallow Neural Network was a secondary check to see if it could handle the task without heavy computing. Text preprocessing included lowercasing, punctuation removal, and whitespace normalization. We balanced training data with stratified sampling and used an 80/20 train-test split with early stopping (patience = 3) for the neural network. Early stopping means the model stops training when its performance on a held-out set stops improving, which prevents overfitting (Prechelt, 1998).

Neither model is state-of-the-art. Transformer models like FinBERT reach 86 to 91% on this dataset (Araci, 2019; Huang et al., 2023), while traditional methods typically achieve 70 to 85% (Nasiopoulos et al., 2025).

We used simpler models because our goal was not to beat benchmarks but to understand where classification fails, especially on the neutral headlines that matter most for our research question.

3.3 Multi-Agent Simulation Design

3.3.1 Purpose and Approach

The simulation tries to address a problem with rule-based agent models: when agents follow fixed rules, the outputs just confirm whatever the researcher put in. Our approach introduces three sources of randomness so that the specific patterns in the output are not predetermined, even though the general kinds of behavior (buying, selling, herding) are built into the rules. The simulation can only produce behaviors that its rules allow. The randomness means we do not know exactly which headlines will cause disagreement or which agents will buy or sell, but the types of behavior are set by the design.

The simulation was built in Python using Google Colab. It processes 2,263 headlines one at a time through 100 computer-generated investor agents, producing 226,300 total decisions.

3.3.2 Sentiment Scoring

We used FinBERT (Araci, 2019) to score each headline. Unlike our Random Forest, which outputs a single label, FinBERT produces a probability distribution across all three classes. For example, a headline might score 60% positive, 30% neutral, and 10% negative. This matters because agents sample from these probabilities randomly rather than getting a fixed score, so the same agent reading the same headline can perceive it differently across runs.

3.3.3 Agent Generation

Rather than designing a fixed set of agent profiles by hand, we generated 100 agents using random values from statistical distributions (Figure 1). Each agent has five core parameters: age (normal distribution centered at 42 with a spread of 12, clipped to 20–75), risk tolerance (inversely correlated with age, range 0.1–0.9), optimism bias (centered near zero with a spread of 0.10), herd susceptibility (centered at 0.15 with a spread of 0.20, where negative values mean contrarian behavior), and reaction style (one of eight types: cautious, aggressive, analytical, balanced, moderate, reactive, contrarian, passive). Parameter ranges were based on investor types described in the behavioral finance literature (Shefrin, 2000; Novianggie & Asandimitra, 2019).

Figure 1: Parameter distributions of the 100 computer-generated investor agents, showing age, risk tolerance, optimism bias, and herd susceptibility.

3.3.4 Three Sources of Randomness

Three mechanisms make the simulation’s outcomes unpredictable. First, randomized perception: each agent samples from FinBERT’s probability distribution, adjusted by their optimism bias and with style-specific noise added (reactive agents: $\sigma = 0.15$; analytical: $\sigma = 0.04$; others: $\sigma = 0.08$). This means the same headline read by the same agent can give a different perceived sentiment each time.

Second, portfolio memory: agents track their recent trading outcomes (up to the last 10 and 20 trades). Losses reduce risk tolerance (up to 40%) faster than gains increase it (up to 30%), with sensitivity varying by personality. Cautious agents have about twice the loss sensitivity of reactive agents, while aggressive agents have about 2.5 times the gain sensitivity of cautious agents. Bad trades make agents more careful faster than good trades make them bolder.

Third, herding dynamics: after each headline, the simulation computes a market consensus score from the previous round’s buy/sell decisions. Each agent blends their own perceived sentiment with this consensus, weighted by their herd susceptibility. No agent can see or talk to other agents directly; the herding effect comes only through the shared consensus signal, similar to how real investors watch market trends without talking to each other.

3.3.5 Decision and Trading Logic

Each agent blends their perceived sentiment score with the market consensus, applies a style-specific modifier (for example, aggressive agents amplify positive signals by $1.2\times$, cautious agents amplify negative signals by $1.3\times$), and compares the result against a threshold set by their risk tolerance. If the blended score exceeds the threshold, the agent buys; if it falls below the negative threshold, the agent sells; otherwise, the agent holds. Trade sizes scale with risk tolerance as a fraction of available cash or stock holdings.

4 Results

4.1 Machine Learning Classification

Table 1: Performance of machine learning models on the FinancialPhraseBank test set (80/20 split).

Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Random Forest	80.2	0.80	0.80	0.80
Shallow Neural Network	70.5	0.71	0.71	0.70

Random Forest performed better at 80.2% accuracy. For comparison, transformer models like FinBERT achieve 86 to 91% accuracy on this dataset (Araci, 2019; Huang et al., 2023), while traditional methods typically get 70 to 85% (Nasiopoulos et al., 2025). Our result falls in the traditional range.

The confusion matrix (Table 2) shows where the model breaks down. It correctly classified 98 of 121 negative sentences (81%) and 103 of 121 positive sentences (85%), but only 90 of 121 neutral sentences (74%). About 26% of neutral headlines were mislabeled as positive or negative. This makes sense because neutral sentences lack the strong signal words that positive and negative ones have. This 26% error rate matters because, as we show below, the headlines machines struggle to classify are also the headlines that produce the most disagreement among simulated investors.

Table 2: Confusion matrix for the Random Forest model. $N = 121$ test sentences per class.

Actual	Pred. Negative	Pred. Neutral	Pred. Positive
Negative (N=121)	98	18	5
Neutral (N=121)	12	90	19
Positive (N=121)	5	13	103

4.2 Simulation Results

4.2.1 Overall Decision Patterns

Across 226,300 decisions (2,263 headlines \times 100 agents), agents produced 71,639 buys (31.7%), 118,897 holds (52.5%), and 35,764 sells (15.8%). Most of the holds are because 61.4% of the headlines in the dataset are neutral, and neutral headlines usually do not push agents past their buy or sell thresholds. Figure 2 shows how actions and perceived sentiment vary across the eight reaction styles. Reactive and aggressive agents bought most often, while passive agents held most often.

Figure 2: Decision distributions across reaction styles: overall action counts (top left), action percentages by style (top right), perceived sentiment by style (bottom left), and average confidence by style (bottom right).

The sentiment-to-action heatmaps (Figure 3) show the expected pattern. When agents perceived a headline as positive, they mostly bought (54,034 buy vs. 1,863 sell). When they perceived negative sentiment, it was the opposite (29,216 sell vs. 3,241 buy), which lines up with H1 and H2. The right heatmap uses the headline’s original expert label instead of the agent’s perception and shows the same thing.

Figure 3: Heatmaps showing the mapping from perceived sentiment to action (left) and from original headline label to action (right) across all 226,300 decisions.

4.2.2 Neutral Headline Disagreement

The biggest difference we found was in how much agents agreed depending on headline sentiment. Agents agreed on 99.1% of negative headlines and 98.1% of positive headlines, but only 89.4% of neutral headlines (Figure 4). The five most divisive headlines, where fewer than half of agents agreed on the same action, were all neutral or near-neutral:

1. “At the end of the review period, Nordic Aluminium’s order book stood at EUR 8.77 mn...” (41% agreement)
2. “Quarterly diluted EPS on continuing operations came in at 0.21 eur...” (45%)
3. “The negotiations concern personnel of Cencorp Corporation...” (46%)
4. “Operating profit totaled EUR 17.7 mn compared to EUR 17.6 mn...” (48%)
5. “Vacon controls a further 5% of the company via investment fund Power Fund I...” (49%)

This lines up with the Random Forest’s performance. The classifier had its highest error rate on neutral headlines (26%), and the simulated agents had their lowest agreement on neutral headlines (89.4%). Both struggle with neutral headlines for what seems to be the same reason: without strong positive or negative signal words, individual differences drive the outcome. For the classifier, those differences are model features; for the agents, they are personality parameters like optimism bias and reaction style. We have not formally tested whether the exact headlines the classifier gets wrong are the same ones agents disagree on (the two used overlapping but different subsets of the data), but we think the parallel is worth noting. This supports H3.

Figure 4: Left: FinBERT ambiguity (1 minus maximum class probability) plotted against agent agreement rate, colored by original sentiment label. Neutral headlines (blue) cluster at lower agreement rates and higher ambiguity. Right: mean agent agreement by headline sentiment category.

4.2.3 Herding Cascades

A herding cascade is when one group of investors starts buying (or selling), and that encourages more investors to do the same, snowballing until something stops it. We defined a herding cascade as any headline where the market consensus score exceeded ± 0.3 . Of the 2,263 headlines, 743 (32.8%) triggered buy cascades and 361 (16.0%) triggered sell cascades (Figure 5). Since each agent has a herd susceptibility parameter and can see the consensus signal, herding-like behavior showing up is not surprising on its own. The part we did not expect was the specific 2:1 ratio of buy to sell cascades, which makes sense in hindsight because the dataset has roughly twice as many positive as negative headlines. Once agents shift toward buying, the higher consensus score encourages more buying in the next round until a negative enough headline breaks the cycle. This feedback

loop shows up in Figure 5, where green shaded regions (buy cascades) often last across several headlines before collapsing.

At first glance, this looks like herding behavior. Devenow & Welch (1996) described herding as investors observing each other's actions and following the crowd, even against their own information. Our agents cannot see each other directly, but the shared consensus signal creates something that looks similar. However, as the ablation tests below show, these cascades barely change when the herding mechanism is turned off, which means something else is going on.

Figure 5: Top: market consensus over time, with green and red shading indicating buy and sell cascade regions. Bottom: distribution of consensus values, showing clustering at the extremes (± 1.0) and near zero.

4.2.4 Loss Aversion Signal

All 100 agents ended the simulation with lower risk tolerance than they started with (mean change: -0.003 , range: -0.020 to approximately 0.000), even though positive headlines outnumbered negative ones roughly 2:1 (Figure 6). So even though agents saw more good news than bad, they all got slightly more careful over time. This was interesting to us at first, but the numbers are really small. Cautious agents showed the largest average shift (-0.0046), about twice that of reactive agents (-0.0020), which fits their higher loss sensitivity parameters. But only 6 of 100 agents went past a change of -0.01 , and no agents became more aggressive. We do not think this is strong evidence for loss aversion appearing on its own in the simulation. The built-in asymmetry in the memory weights probably explains most of it.

Figure 6: Left: starting versus final risk tolerance for each agent, colored by reaction style. Most points fall slightly below the diagonal (more cautious). Right: distribution of risk tolerance changes across all 100 agents.

4.2.5 Ablation Tests

To check whether the findings depend on specific mechanisms or would appear anyway, we ran two more versions of the simulation with key features turned off (Table 3). In Run 2, we set all agents’ herd susceptibility to zero, removing herding entirely. In Run 3, we turned off herding and also made gains and losses update risk tolerance at the same rate, removing the built-in loss aversion.

Table 3: Ablation test results. Run 1 is the baseline. Run 2 turns off herding. Run 3 turns off both herding and unequal memory.

Metric	Run 1 (Baseline)	Run 2 (No herding)	Run 3 (Both off)
Neutral agreement	89.4%	90.4%	92.2%
Positive agreement	98.1%	99.3%	99.4%
Negative agreement	99.1%	99.7%	99.8%
Buy cascades	32.8%	30.1%	28.9%
Sell cascades	16.0%	15.2%	15.2%
Mean risk change	-0.003	-0.0008	-0.0005

The main findings barely changed, which was not what we expected. Buy cascades only dropped from 32.8% to 30.1% without herding and to 28.9% with both features off. This means the cascades are not coming from agents copying each other. They happen because 100 agents independently read the same headline through FinBERT and reach the same conclusion when the sentiment signal is strong enough. When a clearly positive headline appears, almost all agents buy regardless of their personality, because the sentiment signal is strong enough to overpower their differences. From the outside this looks like herding, but it is actually just agents agreeing on their own. We initially expected the herding mechanism to play a bigger role, but the ablation tests showed it barely matters.

The neutral disagreement finding held up across all conditions (89.4%, 90.4%, 92.2%), which confirms that it comes from FinBERT’s real uncertainty on neutral headlines rather than from any agent mechanism. Agents disagree on neutral headlines because the sentiment signal is weak, not because of how we set up the simulation.

The caution shift shrank from -0.003 to -0.0008 to -0.0005 as we removed features, but never fully went away. Even with equal memory weights, agents still drifted very slightly toward caution. But the effect is so small in all conditions that we do not consider it meaningful.

4.2.6 Portfolio Trajectories

Figure 7 shows portfolio value over time for 15 randomly selected agents (left) and average values by reaction style with ± 1 standard deviation bands (right). Analytical agents had the highest average returns, while reactive agents had the lowest. The spread is large: individual agent paths go in very different directions even within the same reaction style, showing how randomized perception and portfolio memory combine to create different trading outcomes from the same headlines.

Figure 7: Left: portfolio trajectories for 15 randomly selected agents, colored by reaction style. Right: average portfolio value by reaction style with ± 1 standard deviation bands.

5 Discussion

Across both parts of this study, neutral sentiment stood out as the category where things break down. The Random Forest misclassified 26% of neutral headlines, compared to 19% for negative and 15% for positive. The simulation showed agents agreeing on only 89.4% of neutral headlines versus 98–99% for clearly positive or negative ones. The two results come from different parts of the dataset, so we cannot say for certain that they are caused by the same thing. But the pattern makes sense: when the signal is clear, personality barely matters and almost everyone buys on strong positive news and sells on strong negative news. When the signal is unclear, individual differences take over. This fits with what Tetlock (2007) found at the market level: clear negative media content predicts price declines, but ambiguous content produces mixed effects.

For practical purposes, this matters because if a sentiment-based trading tool cannot reliably tell neutral headlines apart from weakly positive or negative ones, it risks triggering trades on headlines that should produce no signal (Nasiopoulos et al., 2025). Our confusion matrix shows that 26% of neutral sentences get misrouted, which in a trading system would mean acting on noise.

The herding result was the most surprising to us. We expected the herding mechanism to matter more than it did, but the ablation tests showed that cascades happen at nearly the same rate with or without it. Devenow & Welch (1996) described herding as investors following each other’s actions. What we see is simpler than that: agents all read the same FinBERT output at the same time and independently arrive at the same answer when the sentiment signal is strong enough. There is no copying involved.

The loss aversion signal was in the right direction but too small to matter. The mean risk change shrank from -0.003 at baseline to -0.0008 without herding and -0.0005 with both features off. We do not think this counts as evidence that loss aversion appeared on its own in the simulation. The built-in asymmetry in the memory weights probably explains most of it.

This study has several limitations. The biggest one is that the simulation’s behavior depends on the parameter distributions we chose. We based the ranges on investor types from the literature (Shefrin, 2000; Novianggie & Asandimitra, 2019), but they are not calibrated to real trading data or surveys, so different distributions could produce different results. The FinancialPhraseBank dataset only covers English-language news about compa-

nies on the Finnish stock exchange (OMX Helsinki), which may not generalize to other markets. We also used different subsets for the two parts of the study (4,846 headlines for the classifier, 2,263 for the simulation), so the comparison between them is not as clean as it could be. Finally, we did not run any experiments with real people, which would be the best way to test whether the patterns we found in the simulation actually happen with real investors.

We originally attempted a behavioral experiment with human participants reading headlines from the same dataset, but the pilot had only $N = 7$ respondents and we had not obtained ethics approval beforehand, so we dropped it. A proper follow-up would need SRC/IRB approval and informed consent, with at least $N = 90$ (30 per condition) for adequate statistical power (Cohen, 1988). Running the same headlines through the Random Forest, FinBERT, and human participants would allow a direct three-way comparison. Calibrating agent parameters from survey data or measured personality traits would also strengthen the link between the simulation and real investor behavior.

6 Conclusion

This study looked at how financial news sentiment interacts with investor personality by combining a machine learning classifier with a multi-agent simulation. The Random Forest classifier (80.2% accuracy) showed that neutral sentiment is the hardest category to get right (26% error rate). The simulation, processing 2,263 labeled headlines through 100 randomized agents, showed something similar: neutral headlines generated the most disagreement among agents (89.4% agreement versus 98–99% for positive and negative). Herding cascades appeared in 32.8% and 16.0% of headlines, but ablation tests showed these were mostly agents reaching the same conclusion independently rather than copying each other. A small shift toward caution appeared but was too small to mean much. Out of all the results, the neutral disagreement finding held up the best across every version of the simulation we ran. A follow-up study with human participants would test whether real investors show the same pattern.

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Code Availability

The code and data for this study are available at: <https://github.com/YuvaanshKapila/researchpaper>

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